

Influence of Strategic Change Management Practices On Performance of Oil Marketing Companies in Kenya

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ **Osman Abdi Salat**, MBA student, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology email; oasmo279@yahoo.com. P.O Box 50988-00100 Nairobi-Kenya ⁽²⁾ **Dr. Wario Guyo**, Ph.D. Lecturer, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology

Abstract:

This study aims to investigate the influence of strategic change management practices on performance of oil marketing companies in Kenya. The independent variables were changed leadership and stakeholder engagement. The study was anchored on a descriptive research design. The population of the study comprised of 550 employees of Olympic petroleum limited. The simple random technique was used to select a sample, 83 employees. Primary data was collected through a structured self-administered questionnaire. Data collected was coded, verified for completeness and accuracy data were analyzed using a quantitative approach to derive descriptive statistics/outputs. The study used the Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) to generate reports and the descriptive statistics for various variables in the study. The findings showed that leadership has a positive and significant influence on the firm performance ($\beta_1 = 0.265$, p -value = 0.023). In addition, the findings revealed that stakeholder engagement was shown to have a positive and significant influence on firm performance ($\beta_2 = 0.293$, p -value = 0.008). Thus, the study concluded that stakeholder engagement and leadership are key determinants of Performance of Oil Marketing Companies.

Keywords: leadership, stakeholder engagement, Oil Marketing Companies, Performance

Introduction

Organization's performance is positively influenced by the presence of change management practices which tend to create a significant contribution on firms competencies. According to Horngren (2011) and Anantharaman (2013), organizations link the maximization of performance with change management practices. As a result of intense competition, shorter product life cycles, volatile product and market environments, business firms constantly search for newer sources of competitive advantage, one of the most important being change management practices, that has the potential to improve and determine an organizations fate (Kelliher & Perrett, 2011). In the recent past, there have been increasing empirical evidence (Appelbaum, 2010; Huselid, 2005; Wright, 2009; Schuler and Jackson, 2011) focusing on change management practices and firm performance in oil and petroleum firms because of their contribution in the global economy and the volatile nature of this industry. Buchanan & Boddy, (2009) observes that strategic change is determined by business trends, the environmental factors and the multiple shifts in the global, sociological and political bubble. It can arise due to the anticipations of the stakeholders. It cannot be based on proactive and strategic technique, or in a reactive process in reaction to a crisis within the organization or outside. It may involve fulfilling the changing wants of the marketplace, reducing risk, being more environmentally sensitive, improving the quality, raising consumer satisfaction and staff retention (East, 2011).

Change agents in strategic change must ensure they have established the accurate nature of alterations they face. Change must be viewed as an incident capable of causing many dislocations to the organization's culture, makeup, and outputs (Burnes, 2009). Organizations are facing technological alterations, political, economic, social-cultural alterations, environmental and legal changes (Bevan, 2011). Change is to be done in consultation with the stakeholders it involves otherwise they stand to resist at all levels. Strategic change management in an organization is usually required when changes in technology, the marketplace, information systems, the global economy, social values, workforce demographics and the political environment occur to the environment in which an organization operates (Hoque, 2014).

The environment within which businesses operate is very volatile. The political anxiety, competition from the entrants, social reforms, technological advancement and global changes are some of the challenges that have greatly affected firms. One needs a deep understanding of the environment in order to correctly respond to the market. Failure to correctly respond in time can have devastating consequences (Dess *et al.*, 2006). The above challenges can force a change in the organization, and the organization may only respond to the challenges of the change. Strategic change may be aligned to organization's short-term and long-term strategies of corporate identity, mission and purpose, innovation, customer service and human resource management.

Oil and petroleum industry in Kenya has undergone a metamorphosis over time up to the present day, according to the regulator, Energy Regulatory Commission (2016), 76 companies have been registered for Import, Export and Wholesale business of petroleum products. As noted by Musindi (2008), for many years after independence, the downstream petroleum industry was controlled by only six International Oil Companies. These companies were Shell/Bp, Esso, Caltex, Mobil, Total and Agip. Petroleum is Kenya's major source of commercial energy and has, over the years, accounted for about 80% of the country's commercial energy requirements (Wambui, 2014). However, the trends of this relationship are sharply contrasting and contradicting in the market and economic scenarios in developing countries such as Kenya. According to PIEA, 2015, over the last decade, petroleum products have registered an increased demand, and thus there is a need for increase firm's performance of the business in this sector. A recent survey by Nyikal (2015), showed that strategic change management system of firms in the petroleum industry was found to be inept and completely below the threshold.

In the foregoing, it is interesting to note that the relationship between change management practices and firm performance in the petroleum sector in Kenya contradict the popular empirical and theoretical underpinning that exists. However, there are no studies that explained this deviation. This study, therefore, examines the influence of change management practices on firm performance in oil and petroleum firms in Kenya a case in point Olympic Petroleum K Ltd. Thus, the hypothesized that:

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of change leadership on the performance of Olympic petroleum Kenya limited.

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of stakeholder engagement on the performance of Olympic petroleum Kenya limited.

Theoretical Review

Resource-based view theory emphasizes on how firms can create competitive advantages by resource endowment. A firm that controls distinctive competence over another by virtue of a resource it controls or dominates is likely to perform better than the other that doesn't possess such resource. It adopts two assumptions in analyzing sources of competitive advantage (Peteraf and Barney, 2003). The idea of commitment focuses on the notion that the organization accumulates resources that enable it to have unique competence by establishing long-lasting commitments to defined goals, practices, structures and standards. The issue of firm performance has been central in strategy research for decades and encompasses most other questions that have been raised in the field, for instance, why firms differ, how they behave, how they choose strategies and how they are managed. The idea of resource-based view is that firms compete on their resources and capabilities. This theory supports the variable change leadership.

Organization performance results primarily from managing the extent of dependencies and uncertainties from the environment. Organizations that take precautionary measures to deal with patterns of the environment emerge to shrink adverse environmental impacts on performance. It is expected that resource dependency theory will determine the extent to which environmental dependency and uncertainty act as drivers for an

organization to embark on a variety of controlling strategies to manage the competitive environment to improve organization performance (Nickol, 2006).

Choosing the appropriate strategies in which to proactively influence and thereby control the environment to its advantage should be a consideration in strategic decision-making as this will open an option for the firm to contribute or withhold an important resource or input which can then be used as leverage in bargaining with its partner or customer (Rokkan & Haugland, 2002). Part of the proposition of this theory is that firms can manipulate the environment to their advantage through executing the following strategies; alteration of the environment, diversification, Mergers, and acquisition so that they find a fit for a “negotiated environment and using legal, political and social actions to form a “created environment.

Proponents of Resource Dependency Theory (RDT) suggest that firms should tackle the aspect of increasing dependency and uncertainty by developing dependencies and expand power to its advantage and thus enable the firm to embark on a redistribution of wealth to its gain (Wathne and Heide, 2006) and thereby ensure its constant supply of resources. This theory supports stakeholders’ variable

Conceptual Framework

The above literature clearly anchors all the proposed variables and their relationships, and these are summarized in the following proposed illustration which forms the conceptual framework in the following figure 2.1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

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Literature review

Good change leadership can evolve and sustain an adaptive culture that develops knowledge through purposeful human interaction (Douglas & Wykowski, 2008). This envisages the continuous learning process; cultural diversity can explore and encourage the potential of an organization. Senge (2010) illustrates three foundation characteristics for a person to be in a leadership role in the modern day organizations and they are of an architect, a teacher, and a steward. These three qualities assist in clarifying mission, vision, and values; identifying strategies, structure, and policies; generating efficient learning processes; and facilitating subordinates to develop their mental model continuously and think systematically

Change is an ongoing process. For a successful organization, change is meant to be implemented at three different levels, i.e., individual, group and organization. At every level of change, leadership plays a different

role as it's the virtual duty of a leader to manage the people and make their efforts to be at their best in favor of change for an organization.

Good business leaders create a vision, articulate the vision, passionately own the vision, and relentlessly drive it to completion. Change leadership is very critical and important to the performance of any organization. Changes in technology, socio-demographics, lifestyles, and others have made it difficult for organizations to survive and stay in any stable zone and hence the search for innovation.

Barriers created by peoples' positions have to be broken to encourage better communication in the workplaces (Kanter, Stein & Jick, 2013). The change team leadership need not be too thin compared to the size of the firms and their geographical spread. Where necessary, support teams may have to be created for the overall change team leadership to be effective. Based on this review, the following research question was deduced:

As Douglas & Wykowski (2008) assert, good change leadership can evolve and sustain an adaptive culture that develops knowledge through purposeful human interaction. This envisages the continuous learning process; cultural diversity can explore and encourage the potential of an organization.

Studies carried out by Senge (2010) illustrate three foundation characteristics for a person to be in a leadership role in the modern day organizations. Those characteristics are an architect, teacher, and a steward. These three qualities assist in clarifying mission, vision, and values; identifying strategies, structure, and policies; generating efficient learning processes; and facilitating subordinates to develop their mental model continuously and think systematically.

Whilst most employees may have been given limited opportunities to be involved in the development of organizational change practices; it has not necessarily hindered them from observing and thereby formulating their own views regarding change and change management in their work environment.

A study carried out by Obonyo and Kerongo (2015) suggest three challenges to managing change organization as, organization culture, structure, and leadership. Organizational culture is defined by the nature of variables such as norms, values, and artifacts because they have a direct impact on the behavior of individuals involved. The study further found out that the type of culture observed in an organization is dependent on the type of the managerial style adopted as well as the processes within the organization. The authors further pointed out that the approach that the stakeholders take when faced with challenges are mainly indicated by culture

D'Ortenzio (2012) in his study "understanding change and change management process" found out that strategic change can impact directly or indirectly upon an employee's personal life and the nature of their work. Its impact can be experienced through changed working conditions, benefits, and future aspirations. It is for this reason that it is important that employees are able to understand the change process, analyze its effectiveness, locate their place in it and act by influencing those factors that are affecting them.

Innovation is also a strategic change management practice that is adopted by firms to survive. Chapman (2005) states that business firms need to be innovative as a strategy to ensure their existence since innovations involve ideas that create the future. He further suggests that the quest for the innovations is somewhat doomed unless the managing team who seek it took time to clearly learn from past. Staff training is also a change management practice that is adopted by many firms. Organizations should have continuous training on the change and equipping staff with the necessary skills to effectively carry out the new ways, documentation of the change to provide a

point of reference and uniformity in interpretation and risk assessment in the organization (Musau, 2012).

Kihlgren (2013) states that it is important to realize that people are resistant to change because of the fear of the unknown. One thing stands out that this fear emanates from the environment both internal and external. The study reveals that internal factors are actually the management style and leadership that influence the process of change (Chirimbu, 2011). Smith (2005) considered the inherent conundrum of organizational change: that people, the human resources of organizations, are both an essential factor in organizational change and, at times, the biggest obstacles to achieving change. Therefore, it is concluded that important element for a successful change in any organization is "Leadership." Leaders are known as "Champions of Change"- as it is the top management of any organization who keep the process of change going on and maintaining the operational reliability of the organization (Nadler & Nadler, 2008). Haecel (2009) maintains that the leaders of a firm must not only turn their resources into specific deliverables but that their capabilities must be orchestrated into a coherent system. In other words, the contributions of organization capabilities must be coordinated to help the business in becoming goal oriented.

Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement is a very important strategic change management practices tool in organizational performance. It tends to attach weight to decisions made and carries around the blessings of people in key decisions. To avoid social backlash, an organization needs to build support for its actions through stakeholder engagement. By organizations proactively engaging with its stakeholders helps in identifying potential areas for risks, gridlocks that can result in misunderstanding.

According to (Freeman, Harrison, & Wicks, 2008) a stakeholder is any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of organization's objectives. According to Hitt, Freeman, and Harrison (2008), the use of the term stakeholder emerged in the 1960s from pioneering work at Stanford Research Institute, which argued that managers "needed to understand the concerns of shareholders, employees, lenders, and suppliers, in order to develop objectives that stakeholders could support." The term has become increasingly prevalent since Freeman's (2004) seminal text "Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach." While Freeman explicitly regarded the stakeholder approach to be a strategic management tool - instrumental as opposed to normative - the emergence and establishment of a social performance agenda for business has highlighted the value of stakeholder theory as a "normative approach that some argue is more ethically and morally acceptable than a shareholder value approach" (Cooper, 2004).

There are conflicting ideas about the manner, motivation, and ethics in engaging stakeholders, with the matter of power-equity and mutual trust in the organization stakeholder relationship presenting as a major theme. Greenwood and Van Buren (2010) have identified the construct of "organizational trustworthiness" as a "possible solution to the problem of unfairness in organization stakeholder relations" on the basis that trust necessarily involves a moral component over and above any emotional or rational component ...[and that] trustworthiness is vital to the moral treatment of stakeholders" (Greenwood and Van Buren, 2010).

The basic tenant is that the organization embarks on stakeholder engagement with good intent, i.e., that there are a willingness and capacity to receive and respond to stakeholder feedback in the development of organizational strategies and initiatives that the business responds to the perceptions and views of its stakeholders in ways which accommodate their views and values. Based on this review, the following research question was deduced:

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Change is an ongoing process. For a successful organization, change is meant to be implemented at three different levels; individual, group and organization. At every level of change, leadership plays a different role as it's the virtual duty of a leader to manage the people and make their efforts to be at their best in favor of change for an organization. Barriers created by peoples' positions have to be broken to encourage better communication in the workplaces (Kanter, Stein & Jick 2003). The change team leadership need not be too thin compared to the size of the firms and their geographical spread. Where necessary, support teams may have to be created for the overall change team leadership to be effective. Senior management of the organization has to break ranks and explain the change process at each and every stage and must be on hand to answer relative queries concerning change and be pivotal in the creation of steering teams leading the change process.

Critique of the Literature

Previous studies were done in the past in the same area mainly concentrated on generalization. Senge (2010) illustrates three foundation characteristics for a person to be in a leadership role in the modern day organizations but did not highlight how they correlate to organization performance. Carbon (2007) suggests four key challenges that affect change management practice in companies. The problems included demand for changes by the management team, poor commitment, and inadequate resources to influence changes, lack of common vision and ineffective channels of communication but did not link his study to organization performance.

Kanter et al.,(2003)stated that barriers created by peoples' positions have to be broken to encourage better communication in the workplaces, but they did not discuss how those barriers could be overcome in order to implement strategic change .A study carried out by Obonyo, and Kerongo (2015) suggest three challenges to managing change in an organization as, organization culture, structure, and leadership but they did not show the correlation on stakeholders influence as a challenge. As Douglas & Wykowski (2008) assert, good change leadership can evolve and sustain an adaptive culture that develops knowledge through purposeful human interaction but failed to show how strategic change management can be influenced by leadership.

Material and methods

This study adopted a descriptive research design using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The study focused on all 550 employees working in the following levels: departmental heads, immediate supervisors, and lower cadre employees. This study adopted a random sampling technique in selecting the sample. This also involved random selection of respondents from each stratum. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), 15% of the target population represents an adequate sample for the study. The selected respondents were issued with questionnaires. The study employed the use of Likert scale questionnaire and closed-ended questions. Respondents were presented with descriptive statements in a 5-point Likert scale on which they are required to

rate by scoring the extent to which they perceived a particular statement is descriptive of the force in the corporations. In order to test the reliability of the instruments, internal consistency techniques were applied using Cronbach's Alpha. The alpha value ranges between 0 and 1 with reliability increasing with the increase in value. The coefficient of 0.6 - 0.7 is commonly recommended with 0.7 or higher indicating acceptable reliability. The research adopted content validity which refers to the extent to which a measuring instrument provides adequate coverage of the topic under study. Lefort and Urzua (2008) recommended that instruments used in research should have a CVI of about 0.78. Quantitative data collected were analyzed by descriptive statistics. Further analysis on quantitative data was carried out inferentially using Correlation to show the relationship between independent and dependent variables and ranges from -1 to +1, multiple regression model on SPSS Version 22 to determine the (R^2) magnitude of the relationship that exist between independent variables and dependent variable thus percentage change in the dependent variable can be accounted for by unit change in the independent variable.

$$Y = a + \beta_1 * X_1 + \beta_2 * X_2 + \varepsilon$$

Equation 1: Multiple Regression

Where:

a = Constant (coefficient of intercept)

Y = on the performance of oil marketing companies in Kenya. (Dependent variable)

X_1 = change leadership, X_2 = stakeholder engagement

ε = Error term. $\beta_1 \dots \beta_4$ = regression coefficient of the four variables

Findings

Descriptive statistics

Leadership especially in the area of strategic change management is important because it is anchored on the culture of the organization in the perception of change and thus the role of the leader is important in aligning each member of the organization towards the set culture of change that can enable the performance of the organization to be high even when the change process is running concurrently to the normal day to day activities. The study thus sought to determine the nature of leadership in strategic change management and how it affects firm performance. Stakeholder engagement is a very important strategic change management practices tool in organizational performance. It tends to attach weight to decisions made and carries around the blessings of people in key decisions. To this end, the study thus sought to establish the views of the respondents on whether stakeholder engagement. While firm performance has been discussed widely, there has also been different types of factors that have been pointed out in terms of their influence on firm performance. Organizational performance, in this case, is the attainment of organizational targets. The findings regarding this were presented Table 1

Table 1 Descriptive statistics

	Mean	Std. Dev.
Leadership	3.22	0.937
Stakeholder engagement	4.24	0.999
firm performance	3.22	0.771

Test of hypothesis

From the findings in Table 1, leadership has a positive and significant relationship with firm performance ($r = 0.491$, p -value = 0.000) at 0.01 level of significance. This implies that there is a probability of 0.491 that firm performance will increase with an increase in leadership in strategic change management. The findings also

showed that stakeholder engagement has a positive and significant relationship with firm performance ($r = 0.426$, $p\text{-value} = 0.001$) at 0.01 level of significance means that there is a 0.426 probability that firm performance will increase with an increase in stakeholder engagement. According to Table 1, the R-value is positive (0.722). This means that the variation in firm performance was attributed by 72.2% change in the predictor variables. According to the value of the R-Square, 52.1% of the firm performance could be explained by independent variables of leadership and stakeholder engagement. Therefore, independent 2 showed that the total sum of squares for the regression model was 12.773 while that of the residuals was 11.73. This means that the mean sum of squares for the regression model (total sum of squares for the regression model divided by the degree of freedom (4) was 3.193 while the total residual sum of squares was 0.235 which clearly indicated that the regression model accounted for more than 13 times the variation of the firm performance compared to the residuals, $F\text{-value} = 13.611$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000$.

Table 2: Regression Analysis

	Unstandardized	Standardized Coefficients			correlation zero order
	Coefficients B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	-1.833	0.865		-2.119	0.039
Leadership	0.343	0.146	0.265	2.343	0.023
Stakeholder engagement	0.332	0.12	0.293	2.756	0.008
Model Statistics					
R Square	0.521				
Adjusted R Square	0.483				
F	13.611				
Sig.	0.000a				

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

a. Dependent Variable: Firm performance

Hypothesis one stated that there is no significant influence of leadership on the performance of oil manufacturing firms. The findings in Table 2 showed that leadership has a positive and significant influence on the firm performance ($\beta_1 = 0.265$, $p\text{-value} = 0.023$) and this can be explained further by assessing the value of the t-test which indicates that firm performance would be approximately 2 times higher given the change in mobile banking ($t = 2.243$). This implies that with each unit increase in leadership, firm performance will increase by 0.265 units. These findings affirm that good change leadership can evolve and sustain an adaptive culture that develops knowledge through purposeful human interaction (Douglas & Wykowski, 2008). In this case, change is an ongoing process such that for a successful organization, change is meant to be implemented at three different levels, that is, individual, group and organization. Change leadership is very critical and important to the performance of any organization. Changes in technology, socio-demographics, lifestyles, and others have made it difficult for organizations to survive and stay in any stable zone and hence the search for innovation.

In addition, the findings revealed that stakeholder engagement was shown to have positive and significant influence on firm performance ($\beta_2 = 0.293$, $p\text{-value} = 0.008$) and this can further be evidenced by the value of the t-test which showed that firm performance would be approximately 3 times more given the change in stakeholder engagement ($t = 2.756$). This means that with each unit increase in stakeholder engagement, there will be 0.293 units increase in firm performance. Stakeholder engagement is a very important strategic change management practices tool in organizational performance. It tends to attach weight to decisions made and carries around the blessings of people in key decisions. To avoid social backlash, an organization needs to build

support for its actions through stakeholder engagement. By organizations proactively engaging with its stakeholders helps in identifying potential areas for risks, gridlocks that can result in misunderstanding.

Conclusion

The findings have clearly shown that although leadership positively influences firm performance, there are challenges in terms of the absence of an open door policy which in essence makes the employees feel intimidated by their seniors. Furthermore, although stakeholder engagement positively influences firm performance, there are gaps in terms of involving the employees more and more as stakeholders.

Recommendations

There is need to increase the collaboration among various stakeholders for instance collaboration among different departments in order to improve the relationships at the workplace and reduce the feeling of intimidation and enhance the open door policy that will promote new ideas. This study is an explanatory type of research although mainly focused on Olympic Oil Company Kenya. Although the findings have been concrete, there is need to carry out further research on in other companies that are in the same sector or different sectors in order to enrich the knowledge on strategic change management. Furthermore, there is need to carry out further research in other places in order to enrich the literature and findings in order to refine the recommendations and suggestions to improve the aspect of strategic change management.

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